

On The Computing of Symbolic 2-Plithogenic And 3-Plithogenic Complex Roots of Unity

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Abstract:

The concept of unity roots plays a central role in the theory of field extensions and polynomials roots' computing.

The objective of this paper is to find the algebraic formula for computing the symbolic 2-plithogenic and 3-plithogenic complex roots of unity, where a general formula will be provided with many related examples up to the exponent 3.

Keywords: symbolic 2-plithogenic complex number, symbolic 3-plithogenic complex number, symbolic n-plithogenic roots of unity.

Introduction and preliminaries.

The symbolic n-plithogenic set was supposed by Smarandache in [1-3]. Symbolic n-plithogenic sets were very helpful in algebra, where this concept has helped with developing algebraic structures, where we can see easily that for any value of n, we get a bigger structure.

Symbolic 2-plithogenic structures and 3-plithogenic were defined and handled by many authors around the globe.

For example, by now we have symbolic 2-plithogenic spaces, modules, matrix [4-7], and same thing for 3-plithogenic structures, see [8-11].

In this paper, we are trying to close an important research gap by answering the following question.

How can we find all the roots of unity in the symbolic 2-plithogenic complex ring, and in the 3-plithogenic complex ring?

The symbolic 2-plithogenic or 3-plithogenic root of unity is a symbolic plithogenic number x with the following algebraic property $x^n = \mathbf{1}$.

Definition.

Let C be the complex field, we have:

1). $2 - SP_C = \{v_0 + v_1P_1 + v_2P_2; v_i \in C\}$ is called the symbolic 2-plithogenic complex ring.

2). $3 - SP_C = \{v_0 + v_1P_1 + v_2P_2 + v_3P_3; v_i \in C\}$ is called the symbolic 3-plithogenic complex ring.

Algebraic operations on $2 - SP_C, 3 - SP_C$ are defined as follows:

(+): $2 - SP_C * 2 - SP_C \rightarrow 2 - SP_C$ such that:

$$(v_0 + v_1P_1 + v_2P_2) + (u_0 + u_1P_1 + u_2P_2) = (v_0 + u_0) + (v_1 + u_1)P_1 + (v_2 + u_2)P_2.$$

(+): $3 - SP_C * 3 - SP_C \rightarrow 3 - SP_C$ such that:

$$(v_0 + v_1P_1 + v_2P_2 + v_3P_3) + (u_0 + u_1P_1 + u_2P_2 + u_3P_3) = (v_0 + u_0) + (v_1 + u_1)P_1 + (v_2 + u_2)P_2 + (v_3 + u_3)P_3.$$

(.): $2 - SP_C * 2 - SP_C \rightarrow 2 - SP_C$ such that:

$$(v_0 + v_1P_1 + v_2P_2)(u_0 + u_1P_1 + u_2P_2) = v_0u_0 + (v_0u_1 + v_1u_0 + v_1u_1)P_1 + (v_0u_2 + v_2u_1 + v_2u_2 + v_2u_0 + v_1u_2)P_2.$$

(.): $3 - SP_C * 3 - SP_C \rightarrow 3 - SP_C$ such that:

$$(v_0 + v_1P_1 + v_2P_2 + v_3P_3) \cdot (u_0 + u_1P_1 + u_2P_2 + u_3P_3) = v_0u_0 + (v_0u_1 + v_1u_0 + v_1u_1)P_1 + (v_0u_2 + v_2u_1 + v_2u_2 + v_2u_0 + v_1u_2)P_2 + (v_0u_3 + v_1u_3 + v_2u_3 + v_3u_3 + v_3u_0 + v_3u_1 + v_3u_2)P_3.$$

Multiplication is defined with the following property:

$$P_i \times P_j = P_{\max(i,j)}, P_i \times P_i = P_i; 1 \leq i \leq 3, 1 \leq j \leq 3$$

Main discussion.

Definition.

Let $2 - SP_C$ be the symbolic 2-plithogenic complex ring,

then $v = v_0 + v_1P_1 + v_2P_2 \in 2 - SP_C$ is called n-th root of unity if and only if $v^n = 1$.

Definition.

Let $3 - SP_C$ be the symbolic 2-plithogenic complex ring,

then $v = v_0 + v_1P_1 + v_2P_2 + v_3P_3 \in 3 - SP_C$ is called n-th root of unity if and only if $v^n = 1$.

Definition.

Let $v = v_0 + v_1P_1 + v_2P_2 \in 2 - SP_C, u = u_0 + u_1P_1 + u_2P_2 + u_3P_3 \in 3 - SP_C$, then we define:

$$\bar{v} = \bar{v}_0 + \bar{v}_1P_1 + \bar{v}_2P_2, \bar{u} = \bar{u}_0 + \bar{u}_1P_1 + \bar{u}_2P_2 + \bar{u}_3P_3.$$

Remark.

For $v = v_0 + v_1P_1 + v_2P_2 \in 2 - SP_C$, we have:

$$v^n = v_0^n + [(v_0 + v_1)^n - v_0^n]P_1 + [(v_0 + v_1 + v_2)^n - (v_0 + v_1)^n]P_2; n \in N.$$

For $v = v_0 + v_1P_1 + v_2P_2 + v_3P_3 \in 3 - SP_C$, we have:

$$v^n = v_0^n + [(v_0 + v_1)^n - v_0^n]P_1 + [(v_0 + v_1 + v_2)^n - (v_0 + v_1)^n]P_2 + [(v_0 + v_1 + v_2 + v_3)^n - (v_0 + v_1 + v_2)^n]P_3; n \in N.$$

Theorem.

Let $v = v_0 + v_1P_1 + v_2P_2 \in 2 - SP_C, u = u_0 + u_1P_1 + u_2P_2 + u_3P_3 \in 3 - SP_C$, then:

1. $\|v\| = |v_0| + [|(v_0 + v_1)| - |v_0|]P_1 + [|(v_0 + v_1 + v_2)| - |(v_0 + v_1)|]P_2$
2. $\|u\| = |u_0| + [(u_0 + u_1)| - |u_0|]P_1 + [(u_0 + u_1 + u_2)| - |(u_0 + u_1)|]P_2 + [(u_0 + u_1 + u_2 + u_3)| - |(u_0 + u_1 + u_2)|]P_3$

Proof.

1. $\|v\|^2 = v \cdot \bar{v} = (v_0 + v_1P_1 + v_2P_2)(\bar{v}_0 + \bar{v}_1P_1 + \bar{v}_2P_2) = v_0\bar{v}_0 + (v_0\bar{v}_1 + v_1\bar{v}_0 + v_1\bar{v}_1)P_1 + (v_0\bar{v}_2 + v_2\bar{v}_1 + v_2\bar{v}_2 + v_2\bar{v}_0 + v_1\bar{v}_2)P_2 = |v_0|^2 + ((v_0 + v_1)(\bar{v}_0 + \bar{v}_1) - v_0\bar{v}_0)P_1 + ((v_0 + v_1 + v_2)(\bar{v}_0 + \bar{v}_1 + \bar{v}_2) - (v_0 + v_1)(\bar{v}_0 + \bar{v}_1))P_2 = |v_0|^2 + [|(v_0 + v_1)|^2 - |v_0|^2]P_1 + [|(v_0 + v_1 + v_2)|^2 - |(v_0 + v_1)|^2]P_2$

Now, we put

$$R = |v_0| + [|(v_0 + v_1)| - |v_0|]P_1 + [|(v_0 + v_1 + v_2)| - |(v_0 + v_1)|]P_2.$$

We get

$$\begin{aligned} R^2 &= |v_0|^2 + [|(v_0 + v_1)|^2 - |v_0|^2]P_1 + [|(v_0 + v_1 + v_2)|^2 - |(v_0 + v_1)|^2]P_2 \\ &\quad + 2|v_0|P_1[|(v_0 + v_1)| - |v_0|] + 2|v_0|[|(v_0 + v_1 + v_2)| - |(v_0 + v_1)|]P_2 \\ &\quad + 2(|(v_0 + v_1)| - |v_0|)[|(v_0 + v_1 + v_2)| - |(v_0 + v_1)|]P_1P_2 \\ &= |v_0|^2 \\ &\quad + [|(v_0 + v_1)|^2 - |v_0|^2 - 2|v_0||v_0 + v_1| + 2|v_0||v_0 + v_1| - 2|v_0|^2]P_1 \\ &\quad + [|(v_0 + v_1 + v_2)|^2 - |(v_0 + v_1)|^2 + 2|v_0 + v_1||v_0 + v_1 + v_2| \\ &\quad + 2|v_0||v_0 + v_1 + v_2| - 2|v_0||v_0 + v_1| + 2|v_0 + v_1||v_0 + v_1 + v_2| \\ &\quad - |v_0 + v_1|^2 - 2|v_0||v_0 + v_1 + v_2| + 2|v_0||v_0 + v_1|]P_2 \\ &= |v_0|^2 + [|(v_0 + v_1)|^2 - |v_0|^2]P_1 + [|(v_0 + v_1 + v_2)|^2 - |(v_0 + v_1)|^2]P_2 \end{aligned}$$

This implies that

$$\|v\| = R = |v_0| + [|(v_0 + v_1)| - |v_0|]P_1 + [|(v_0 + v_1 + v_2)| - |(v_0 + v_1)|]P_2.$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2. \|u\|^2 &= u \cdot \bar{u} = (u_0 + u_1P_1 + u_2P_2 + u_3P_3)(\bar{u}_0 + \bar{u}_1P_1 + \bar{u}_2P_2 + \bar{u}_3P_3) = u_0\bar{u}_0 + \\ &\quad (u_0\bar{u}_1 + u_1\bar{u}_0 + u_1\bar{u}_1)P_1 + (u_0\bar{u}_2 + u_2\bar{u}_1 + u_2\bar{u}_2 + u_2\bar{u}_0 + u_1\bar{u}_2)P_2 + \\ &\quad (u_0\bar{u}_3 + u_1\bar{u}_3 + u_2\bar{u}_3 + u_3\bar{u}_0 + u_3\bar{u}_1 + u_3\bar{u}_2 + u_3\bar{u}_3)P_3 = |u_0|^2 + ((u_0 + \\ &\quad u_1)(\bar{u}_0 + \bar{u}_1) - u_0\bar{u}_0)P_1 + ((u_0 + u_1 + u_2)(\bar{u}_0 + \bar{u}_1 + \bar{u}_2) - (u_0 + u_1)(\bar{u}_0 + \\ &\quad \bar{u}_1))P_2 + ((u_0 + u_1 + u_2 + u_3)(\bar{u}_0 + \bar{u}_1 + \bar{u}_2 + \bar{u}_3) - (u_0 + u_1 + u_2)(\bar{u}_0 + \bar{u}_1 + \\ &\quad \bar{u}_2))P_3 = |u_0|^2 + [(u_0 + u_1)^2 - |u_0|^2]P_1 + [(u_0 + u_1 + u_2)^2 - |(u_0 + \\ &\quad u_1)|^2]P_2 + [(u_0 + u_1 + u_2 + u_3)^2 - |(u_0 + u_1 + u_2)|^2]P_3 \end{aligned}$$

We put

$$R = |u_0| + [|(u_0 + u_1)| - |u_0|]P_1 + [|(u_0 + u_1 + u_2)| - |(u_0 + u_1)|]P_2 + [|(u_0 + u_1 + u_2 + u_3)| - |(u_0 + u_1 + u_2)|]P_3$$

by an easy computing, we get $R^2 = |u|^2$, thus $|u| = R$.

Example.

Take $v = (2 + i) + (1 - i)P_1 + 2iP_2 \in 2 - SP_C$, we have:

$$v_0 = 2 + i, v_1 = 1 - i, v_2 = 2i.$$

$$\bar{v}_0 = 2 - i, \bar{v}_1 = 1 + i, \bar{v}_2 = -2i$$

$$\bar{v} = (2 - i) + (1 + i)P_1 - 2iP_2$$

$$\text{Also, } \begin{cases} |v_0| = \sqrt{5}, |v_0 + v_1| = |3| = 3, |v_0 + v_1 + v_2| = |3 + 2i| = \sqrt{13} \\ \|v\| = \sqrt{5} + (3 - \sqrt{5})P_1 + (\sqrt{13} - 3)P_2 \end{cases}$$

Example.

Take $v = (1 + i) + (1 - 3i)P_1 + (5 + i)P_2 + (4 + 3i)P_3$, we have:

$$v_0 = 1 + i, v_1 = 1 - 3i, v_2 = 5 + i, v_3 = 4 + 3i.$$

$$\bar{v}_0 = 1 - i, \bar{v}_1 = 1 + 3i, \bar{v}_2 = 5 - i, \bar{v}_3 = 4 - 3i$$

$$\bar{v} = 1 - i + (1 + 3i)P_1 + (5 - i)P_2 + (4 - 3i)P_3$$

Also,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} |v_0| = \sqrt{2}, |v_0 + v_1| = |2 - 2i| = \sqrt{8}, |v_0 + v_1 + v_2| = |7 - i| = \sqrt{50}, |v_0 + v_1 + v_2 + v_3| = |11 + 2i| \\ \|v\| = \sqrt{2} + (\sqrt{8} - \sqrt{2})P_1 + (\sqrt{50} - \sqrt{8})P_2 + (\sqrt{125} - \sqrt{50})P_3 \end{array} \right.$$

Theorem.

Let $v = v_0 + v_1P_1 + v_2P_2 \in 2 - SP_C$, then v is a symbolic 2-plithogenic n-th root of unity if and only if $v_0, v_0 + v_1, v_0 + v_1 + v_2$ are classical n-th roots of unity in the field C .

Proof.

It is know $v^n = 1$, which is equivalent to:

$$v_0^n + [(v_0 + v_1)^n - v_0^n]P_1 + [(v_0 + v_1 + v_2)^n - (v_0 + v_1)^n]P_2 = 1$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} v_0^n = 1 \\ (v_0 + v_1)^n - v_0^n = 0 \Rightarrow (v_0 + v_1)^n = v_0^n = 1 \\ (v_0 + v_1 + v_2)^n - (v_0 + v_1)^n = 0 \Rightarrow (v_0 + v_1 + v_2)^n = (v_0 + v_1)^n = 1 \end{array} \right.$$

So that, $v_0, v_0 + v_1, v_0 + v_1 + v_2$ are n-th roots of unity.

Example.

Let us find all a symbolic 2-plithogenic roots of unity order 2.

The classical set of the roots of unity of order 2 is $E_1 = \{-1, 1\}$.

The corresponding 2-symbolic plithogenic roots of unity of order 2 are:

- 1). $v_0 = v_0 + v_1 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = 1 \Rightarrow R_1 = 1$
- 2). $v_0 = v_0 + v_1 = 1, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = -1 \Rightarrow R_2 = 1 - 2P_2$
- 3). $v_0 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = 1, v_0 + v_1 = -1 \Rightarrow R_3 = 1 - 2P_1 + 2P_2$
- 4). $v_0 = 1, v_0 + v_1 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = -1 \Rightarrow R_4 = 1 - 2P_1$
- 5). $v_0 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = 1 = v_0 + v_1 = -1 \Rightarrow R_5 = -1$
- 6). $v_0 = v_0 + v_1 = -1, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = 1 \Rightarrow R_6 = -1 + 2P_2$
- 7). $v_0 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = -1, v_0 + v_1 = -1 \Rightarrow R_7 = -1 + 2P_1 - 2P_2$

$$8). v_0 = -1, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = v_0 + v_1 = 1 \Rightarrow R_8 = -1 + 2P_1$$

Example.

Let us find all a symbolic 2-plithogenic roots of unity order 3.

The classical set of the roots of unity of order 3 is $E_2 = \{-1, e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}, e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i}\}$.

The corresponding 2-symbolic plithogenic roots of unity of order 3 are:

$$1). v_0 = v_0 + v_1 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = 1 \Rightarrow R_1 = 1$$

$$2). v_0 = v_0 + v_1 = 1, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_2 = 1 + (e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} - 1)P_2$$

$$3). v_0 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = 1, v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_3 = 1 + (e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} - 1)P_2$$

$$4). v_0 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = 1, v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_4 = 1 + (e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} - 1)P_1 + (e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} - 1)P_2$$

$$5). v_0 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = 1 = v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_5 = 1 + (e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} - 1)P_1 + (1 - e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i})P_2$$

$$6). v_0 = 1, v_0 + v_1 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_6 = 1 + (e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} - 1)P_1$$

$$7). v_0 = 1, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_7 = 1 + (e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} - 1)P_2$$

$$8). v_0 = 1, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_8 = 1 + (e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} - 1)P_1 + (e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} - e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i})P_2$$

$$9). v_0 = 1, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_9 = 1 + (e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} - 1)P_1 + (e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} - e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i})P_2$$

$$10). v_0 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = v_0 + v_1 = 1 \Rightarrow R_{10} = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} + (1 - e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i})P_1$$

$$11). v_0 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_{11} = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}$$

$$12). v_0 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_{12} = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} + (e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} - e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i})P_1$$

$$13). v_0 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 = 1 \Rightarrow R_{13} = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} + (1 - e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i})P_1 + (e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} - 1)P_2$$

$$14). v_0 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 = 1 \Rightarrow R_{14} = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} + (1 - e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i})P_1 + (e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} - 1)P_2$$

$$15). v_0 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = 1, v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_{15} = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} + (1 - e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i})P_2$$

$$16). v_0 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = 1, v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_{16} = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} + \left(e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} - e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} \right) P_1 + \left(1 - e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \right) P_2$$

$$17). v_0 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_{17} = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} + \left(e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} - e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} \right) P_2$$

$$18). v_0 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_{18} = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} + \left(e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} - e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} \right) P_1 + \left(e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} - e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \right) P_2$$

$$19). v_0 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = v_0 + v_1 = 1 \Rightarrow R_{19} = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} + \left(1 - e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \right) P_1$$

$$20). v_0 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_{20} = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} + \left(e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} - e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \right) P_1$$

$$21). v_0 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_{21} = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i}$$

$$22). v_0 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 = 1 \Rightarrow R_{22} = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} + \left(1 - e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \right) P_1 + \left(e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} - 1 \right) P_2$$

$$23). v_0 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 = 1 \Rightarrow R_{23} = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} + \left(1 - e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \right) P_1 + \left(e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} - 1 \right) P_2$$

$$24). v_0 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = 1, v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_{24} = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} + \left(e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} - e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \right) P_1 + \left(1 - e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} \right) P_2$$

$$25). v_0 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = 1, v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_{25} = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} + \left(1 - e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \right) P_2$$

$$26). v_0 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_{26} = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} + \left(e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} - e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \right) P_1 + \left(e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} - e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} \right) P_2$$

$$27). v_0 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i}, v_0 + v_1 = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \Rightarrow R_{27} = e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} + \left(e^{\frac{2\pi}{3}i} - e^{\frac{4\pi}{3}i} \right) P_2$$

Theorem.

Let $v = v_0 + v_1P_1 + v_2P_2 + v_3P_3 \in 3 - SP_C$, then v is an n-th root of unity if and only if $v_0, v_0 + v_1, v_0 + v_1 + v_2$ are n-th root of unity in C .

Proof.

It is know that $v^n = 1$, which is equivalent to:

$$v_0^n + [(v_0 + v_1)^n - v_0^n]P_1 + [(v_0 + v_1 + v_2)^n - (v_0 + v_1)^n]P_2 + [(v_0 + v_1 + v_2 + v_3)^n - (v_0 + v_1 + v_2)^n]P_3 = 1$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} v_0^n = 1 \\ (v_0 + v_1)^n - v_0^n = 0 \Rightarrow (v_0 + v_1)^n = v_0^n = 1 \\ (v_0 + v_1 + v_2)^n - (v_0 + v_1)^n = 0 \Rightarrow (v_0 + v_1 + v_2)^n = (v_0 + v_1)^n = 1 \\ (v_0 + v_1 + v_2 + v_3)^n - (v_0 + v_1 + v_2)^n = 0 \Rightarrow (v_0 + v_1 + v_2 + v_3)^n = (v_0 + v_1 + v_2)^n = 1 \end{array} \right.$$

Thus the proof holds.

Example.

Let us find all of 2-nd roots of unity in $3 - SP_C$.

- 1). $v_0 = v_0 + v_1 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 + v_3 = 1 \Rightarrow R_1 = 1$
- 2). $v_0 = v_0 + v_1 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = 1, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 + v_3 = -1 \Rightarrow R_2 = 1 - 2P_3$
- 3). $v_0 = v_0 + v_1 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 + v_3 = 1, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = -1 \Rightarrow R_3 = 1 - 2P_2 + 2P_3$
- 4). $v_0 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 + v_3 = 1, v_0 + v_1 = -1 \Rightarrow R_4 = 1 - 2P_1 + 2P_2$
- 5). $v_0 = v_0 + v_1 = 1, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 + v_3 = -1 \Rightarrow R_5 = 1 - 2P_2$
- 6). $v_0 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = 1, v_0 + v_1 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 + v_3 = -1 \Rightarrow R_6 = 1 + 2P_2 + 2P_3$
- 7). $v_0 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 + v_3 = 1, v_0 + v_1 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = -1 \Rightarrow R_7 = 1 - 2P_1 + 2P_3$
- 8). $v_0 = 1, v_0 + v_1 + v_2 + v_3 = v_0 + v_1 = v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = -1 \Rightarrow R_8 = 1 - 2P_1$
- 9). $R_9 = -1 = -R_1$
- 10). $R_{10} = -R_2 = -1 + 2P_3$
- 11). $R_{11} = -R_3 = -1 + 2P_2 - 2P_3$
- 12). $R_{12} = -R_4 = -1 + 2P_1 - 2P_2$
- 13). $R_{13} = -R_5 = -1 + 2P_2$
- 14). $R_{14} = -R_6 = -1 - 2P_2 - 2P_3$
- 15). $R_{15} = -R_7 = -1 + 2P_1 - 2P_3$
- 16). $R_{16} = -R_8 = -1 + 2P_1$.

The group of unity roots classification

It is known that the set of all n-th roots of unity forms a subgroup of C^* denoted by U_C with respect to the multiplication operation and this group is isomorphic to the additive group Z_n (integers modulo n).

By a similar approach, we can see easily that the set of all symbolic 2-plithogenic complex n-th roots of unity forms a group with respect to multiplication operation,

and the set of all symbolic 3-plithogenic complex n-th roots of unity forms a group with respect to multiplication operation.

The following theorem classifies the symbolic 2-plithogenic and 3-plithogenic groups of n-th roots of unity.

Theorem:

Let U_{2-SPC} be the group of n-th unity roots of symbolic 2-plithogenic complex numbers, and U_{3-SPC} be the group of n-th unity roots of symbolic 3-plithogenic complex numbers, then:

$$1-) U_{2-SPC} \cong Z_n \times Z_n \times Z_n.$$

$$2-) U_{3-SPC} \cong Z_n \times Z_n \times Z_n \times Z_n.$$

Proof:

1-) Define the mapping $f: U_{2-SPC} \rightarrow U_C \times U_C \times U_C$ such that:

$$f(e_0 + e_1P_1 + e_2P_2) = (e_0, e_0 + e_1, e_0 + e_1 + e_2).$$

The mapping f is well defined:

For $M = m_0 + m_1P_1 + m_2P_2 = N = n_0 + n_1P_1 + n_2P_2$, we get:

$$m_0 = n_0, m_0 + m_1 = n_0 + n_1, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = n_0 + n_1 + n_2,$$

Thus $f(M) = f(N)$.

The mapping f preserves multiplication:

For $M = m_0 + m_1P_1 + m_2P_2, N = n_0 + n_1P_1 + n_2P_2$, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} f(MN) &= f(m_0n_0 + [m_0n_1 + m_1n_0 + m_1n_1]P_1 + [m_0n_2 + m_1n_2 + m_2n_0 + m_2n_1 + \\ & m_2n_2]P_2) = (m_0n_0, m_0n_0 + m_0n_1 + m_1n_0 + m_1n_1, m_0n_0 + m_0n_1 + m_1n_0 + m_1n_1 + \\ & m_0n_2 + m_1n_2 + m_2n_0 + m_2n_1 + m_2n_2) = (m_0, m_0 + m_1, m_0 + m_1 + m_2). (n_0, n_0 + \\ & n_1, n_0 + n_1 + n_2) = f(M)f(N). \end{aligned}$$

The mapping f is injective:

$$\text{Ker}(f) = \{M = m_0 + m_1P_1 + m_2P_2; f(M) = (1,1,1)\},$$

So that, $m_0 = 1, m_1 = m_2 = 0$, thus $\text{Ker}(f) = \{1\}$.

The mapping f is surjective:

$$\text{Im}(f) = U_C \times U_C \times U_C.$$

Thus, the mapping f is a group isomorphism, which means that $U_{2-SPC} \cong U_C \times U_C \times U_C$. Since $U_C \cong Z_n$, we get $U_{2-SPC} \cong Z_n \times Z_n \times Z_n$.

2-) Define the mapping $f: U_{3-SPC} \rightarrow U_C \times U_C \times U_C \times U_C$ such that:

$$f(e_0 + e_1P_1 + e_2P_2) = (e_0, e_0 + e_1, e_0 + e_1 + e_2, e_0 + e_1 + e_2 + e_3).$$

The mapping f is well defined:

For $M = m_0 + m_1P_1 + m_2P_2 + m_3P_3 = N = n_0 + n_1P_1 + n_2P_2 + n_3P_3$, we get:

$$m_0 = n_0, m_0 + m_1 = n_0 + n_1, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 = n_0 + n_1 + n_2, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 + m_3 = n_0 + n_1 + n_2 + n_3,$$

Thus $f(M) = f(N)$.

The mapping f preserves multiplication:

For $M = m_0 + m_1P_1 + m_2P_2 + m_3P_3, N = n_0 + n_1P_1 + n_2P_2 + n_3P_3$, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} f(MN) &= f(m_0n_0 + [m_0n_1 + m_1n_0 + m_1n_1]P_1 + [m_0n_2 + m_1n_2 + m_2n_0 + m_2n_1 + \\ & m_2n_2]P_2 + [m_0n_3 + m_1n_3 + m_2n_3 + m_3n_0 + m_3n_1 + m_3n_2 + m_3n_3]P_3) = \\ & (m_0n_0, m_0n_0 + m_0n_1 + m_1n_0 + m_1n_1, m_0n_0 + m_0n_1 + m_1n_0 + m_1n_1 + m_0n_2 + \\ & m_1n_2 + m_2n_0 + m_2n_1 + m_2n_2, m_0n_0 + m_0n_1 + m_1n_0 + m_1n_1 + m_0n_2 + m_1n_2 + \\ & m_2n_0 + m_2n_1 + m_2n_2 + m_0n_3 + m_1n_3 + m_2n_3 + m_3n_0 + m_3n_1 + m_3n_2 + m_3n_3) = \\ & (m_0, m_0 + m_1, m_0 + m_1 + m_2, m_0 + m_1 + m_2 + m_3). (n_0, n_0 + n_1, n_0 + n_1 + n_2, n_0 + \\ & n_1 + n_2 + n_3) = f(M)f(N). \end{aligned}$$

The mapping f is injective:

$$\text{Ker}(f) = \{M = m_0 + m_1P_1 + m_2P_2 + m_3P_3; f(M) = (1,1,1)\},$$

So that, $m_0 = 1, m_1 = m_2 = m_3 = 0$, thus $\text{Ker}(f) = \{1\}$.

The mapping f is surjective:

$$\text{Im}(f) = U_C \times U_C \times U_C \times U_C.$$

Thus, the mapping f is a group isomorphism, which means that $U_{3-SPC} \cong U_C \times U_C \times U_C \times U_C$. Since $U_C \cong Z_n$, we get $U_{3-SPC} \cong Z_n \times Z_n \times Z_n \times Z_n$.

Conclusion.

In this paper, we presented an algebraic algorithm to compute n-th roots of unity in symbolic 2-plithogenic/3-plithogenic complex ring respectively.

Also, we have illustrated some examples to clarify the flow of our algorithm.

In the future, we aim to find n -th roots of unity in symbolic m -plithogenic complex ring for any value of m .

References:

1. Smarandache, F., " Introduction to the Symbolic Plithogenic Algebraic Structures (revisited)", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, vol. 53, 2023.
2. Florentin Smarandache, Plithogenic Algebraic Structures. Chapter in "Nidus idearum Scilogs, V: joining the dots" (third version), Pons Publishing Brussels, pp. 123-125, 2019.
3. Florentin Smarandache: Plithogenic Set, an Extension of Crisp, Fuzzy, Intuitionistic Fuzzy, and Neutrosophic Sets – Revisited, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 21, 2018, pp. 153-166.
4. Alfahal, A., Alhasan, Y., Abdulfatah, R., Mehmood, A., and Kadhim, M., " On Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Real Matrices and Their Algebraic Properties", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Vol 21, 2023.
5. Nader Mahmoud Taffach , Ahmed Hatip., "A Review on Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Algebraic Structures " *Galoitica Journal Of Mathematical Structures and Applications*, Vol.5, 2023.
6. M. B. Zeina, N. Altounji, M. Abobala, and Y. Karmouta, "Introduction to Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Probability Theory," *Galoitica: Journal of Mathematical Structures and Applications*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2023.
7. Merkepçi, H., and Abobala, M., " On The Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Rings", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, 2023.
8. Ali, R., and Hasan, Z., " An Introduction To The Symbolic 3-Plithogenic Modules ", *Galoitica Journal Of Mathematical Structures and Applications*, vol. 6, 2023.
9. Ali, R., and Hasan, Z., "An Introduction To The Symbolic 3-Plithogenic Vector Spaces", *Galoitica Journal Of Mathematical Structures and Applications*, vol. 6, 2023.

10. Rawashdeh, A., "An Introduction To The Symbolic 3-plithogenic Number Theory", *Neoma Journal Of Mathematics and Computer Science*, 2023.
11. Ben Othman, K., "On Some Algorithms For Solving Symbolic 3-Plithogenic Equations", *Neoma Journal Of Mathematics and Computer Science*, 2023.
12. Ben Othman, K., Von Shtawzen, O., Khaldi, A., and Ali, R., "On The Concept Of Symbolic 7-Plithogenic Real Matrices", *Pure Mathematics For Theoretical Computer Science, Vol.1*, 2023.
13. Ben Othman, K., Von Shtawzen, O., Khaldi, A., and Ali, R., "On The Symbolic 8-Plithogenic Matrices", *Pure Mathematics For Theoretical Computer Science, Vol.1*, 2023.
14. Ben Othman, K., Albasheer, O., Nadweh, R., Von Shtawzen, O., and Ali, R., "On The Symbolic 6-Plithogenic and 7-Plithogenic Rings", *Galoitica Journal of Mathematical Structures and Applications, Vol.8*, 2023.

Received 19/7/2023, Accepted 5/9/2023